

FACTORS OF INCREASING SPIRITUAL EDUCATION AND INFORMATION CULTURE OF YOUTH

Khudaiberdiev A.K.

Associate Professor at Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12608951>

Abstract. *In this article a special attention is paid to the approaches related to improving the quality of education at the new stage of development of Uzbekistan, improving the moral education of youth through the introduction of modern teaching methods at all stages of the lifelong education system, as well as improving information culture.*

Keywords: *state youth policy, quality of education, spiritual education of youth, creative thinking, investment, information culture.*

Introduction. It is known that our country is one of the fastest growing countries in the world. It ranks first in Central Asia in terms of population and in Asia in terms of the percentage of youth. Such indicators and characteristics of the demography of our country, in turn, are considered one of the factors that have a great influence on all areas of development of our society, especially on the dynamics of spiritual life. It follows that this factor is of particular importance in the politics of any state. In particular, in our country this factor is taken into account in state policy towards youth, and attention is paid to the effective use of their creative power.

Literature review. It is known that the constant growth of the population of our country affects processes in all spheres of society and is one of the important factors that should be taken into account in the social policy of the state. It should be noted that the population of our country increased by 1.5 times compared to 1991 and by 9.3% compared to 2013 (36.5 million people). Of these, 19.6 million young people under the age of 30 make up 59.1% of the population. The largest number of young people was recorded in Samarkand (2.2 million) and Fergana (2.02 million) regions, and the smallest number was recorded in Syrdarya (0.48 thousand) and Navoi (0.53 thousand) regions. An analysis of demographic indicators shows that as of January 2014, youth accounted for 57% of the total population, and in 2024 it will be 59.1%.

Based on the above information, it can be said that in order to further democratize and liberalize society and implement fundamental reforms in important areas of the country's life, it is necessary to develop new methods and make maximum use of them to increase the efficiency of work carried out with youth. In this regard, it should be noted that the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, adopted in 1992, became an important step in this direction. Also, the "Family Code", "National Personnel Training Program", "On Guarantees of Children's Rights", "On Education", "Population Affairs" were developed by our government on the basis of the national and universal principles of "On Security". "On physical education and sports", "On the prevention of lack of control and delinquency among minors", "On guardianship and trusteeship". A number of regulatory documents "O" in the first years of independence in our country indicate that state policy in this area was formed and a legal basis was created for it.

Research Methodology. In this sense, it is not without reason that at the very beginning of independence, the formation of a generation takes place that will serve the bright future of our country, its worthy place on the world stage, morally and physically mature, who have mastered modern science, was identified as one of the pressing problems. Soon after the declaration of

independence, on November 20, 1991, the Law “On the fundamentals of state policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan regarding youth” was announced (adopted in a new edition on September 14, 2016). A clear confirmation of this is the fact that such a document has not been created in any country of the former union.

It means that due to such documents, when it is put into circulation in the first years of independence, indicate that, like all spheres of life in our society, the priority principles of the youth policy of our country, which is the main reformer in this regard, were determined in the first steps our path of development. At present time, instead of it, in the established practice of state policy regarding youth in our country, it is planned to further expand the work on maturing young people in all aspects, supporting plans for the future and socially oriented measures.

In this process, the Law “On Education” (adopted in a new edition on September 23, 2020) and the “National Personnel Training Program” were used to develop positive methods and solutions that serve the effectiveness of policy in our country. Accepted from the very beginning, the issue of careful study of the problems associated with the successful solution of the assigned tasks is of particular importance.

As a result of the work carried out locally in recent years, in different years, in order to demonstrate the abilities of talented youth, such funds as “Umid”, “Ustoz”, “Iste’dod” were created, three-stage tournaments were organized in the field of physical education and sports, such as “Umid Nihollari”, “Barkamol Avlod”, “Universiade”. State awards “Nikhol”, “Zulfiya”, “Brave Boy”, “Builder of the Future” were established, showing the qualities of patriotism, dedication and hard work, as well as activity and initiative in social and political life. our country, he was recognized by his peers. It was decided to present these awards to young people who have achieved success, as well as great progress in their studies and work, who have reached 14 years of age and have not reached 30 years of age. years.

At present time, much attention was paid to the issue of providing young people with every opportunity to study in their desired specialty, work in fair conditions, and actively participate in international and local Olympiads, competitions and competitions. And if we say that this opened the doors of opportunities for them to be active in all directions and spheres of social life, to regularly participate in spiritual, economic, sports, educational and other events, we would understate the truth.

In this regard, it should be noted that in the current period there is a need to search for modern and effective methods for the consistent implementation of our country’s youth policy and to achieve the participation of youth representatives in this process. The election program of the President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev states: “We are serious about creating an effective system for training new and independent thinking, responsible and proactive, advanced management methods, honest personnel devoted to their country and people.” work" is a clear confirmation of this.

On June 30, 2018, on the eve of “Youth Day”, the President of the Republic presented the new State program “Youth is our future”, and the implementation of practical work in all areas of the program is another step. Inextricably linked with this, the Decree on the State Program “Youth is our Future”, approved on June 27, 2018, is considered one of the important historical documents implemented in our country with the aim of supporting the younger generation and providing them with ample opportunities. A factor that increases the significance of the decree in the life of society are young men and women under 30 years of age, who make up 60 percent of the population of

our country. The significance of this Decree in solving the problems facing the current generation and in intensifying its activity is incomparable.

Nowadays it is the key to further activation of the youth factor and wider development of its potential. The leading principles in this matter are determined by the following opinion of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev: “At present time, the period requires increasing the effectiveness of activities aimed at promoting legal culture, a healthy lifestyle, physical education and sports among our youth. The implementation of the program's measures in this direction will continue strictly on the basis of the provisions of the law “On State Policy towards Youth,” which was recently adopted. A natural question arises here. We are adopting many programs, but do we have enough proactive, patriotic, highly qualified personnel to implement them? Are specialists trained in higher educational institutions capable of fulfilling such enormous tasks facing us? Are the knowledge and skills of the teachers and professors who teach them up to date with the demands of the times? Unfortunately, these questions are not easy to answer.”

Analysis and results. The above opinions are related to one of the painful aspects of our time, the peculiarities of the youth policy pursued by the head of state, an in-depth study and analysis of leading criteria and characteristics, as well as increasing the effectiveness of reform in all spheres of public life, spiritual youth and puts on the agenda such issues as the development of factors related to physical maturity. Along with this, the task of creating a fundamentally renewed society has been raised to a new level, which will lead to the rapid development and prosperity of our country in accordance with the pace of the times, joining the ranks of the strongest countries in the world. level.

The condition in this situation is the development of our children into young people capable of meeting the demands of tense times, serving the interests of the Motherland and the nation, becoming not only physically and spiritually perfect, but also possessing advanced knowledge and experience. It is not for nothing that it is defined as an urgent task of the country's politics. This is evidenced by the “Strategy for the Development of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026,” which is its logical continuation, approved by the Presidential Decree, and the “Uzbekistan-2030” strategy, adopted on September 11, 2023.

In the above-mentioned decrees and resolutions, in the course of changes and updates throughout society, priority is given to the issue of educating young people as comprehensively developed individuals who have mastered the laws of democracy, developing their intellectual potential, and increasing their spiritual and educational consciousness.

Definitely, at present time when globalization processes have intensified throughout the world, various events and incidents are taking place in international arenas, there is a threat of destructive ideas and destructive ideologies developing in ideological grounds and arenas, as well as the threat of foreign and destructive ideologies. ideology, the importance of youth policy reforms increases significantly, which means that the weight of tasks in this direction increases.

President Shavkat Mirziyoyev comments on this: “At today’s rapidly changing world is opening up new and greater opportunities for humanity and youth. At the same time, they are exposed to various evil dangers that they have never seen before. Evil forces turn simple, gullible children against their parents, their country and deprive them of their lives. In such a tense and dangerous situation, we as parents, teachers, communities and the public must increase our vigilance and awareness on this issue. We should raise our children ourselves and not leave them in the hands of others.” Based on this, we can say that the further strengthening of the independence

of the state in the modern world largely depends on the spiritual perfection, high intellectual qualities, professional and scientific activity of young people - the masters of the future, who harmonize the demands of the time and national thinking. Only the young generation, which does not forget its national identity, is capable of developing the ability for independent and critical thinking, has a sharp mind, and can build a prosperous future.

That is why the main task of the state and society is to cultivate such qualities in young men and women. The specific requirements of fast and dynamic life require that the state be the main reformer in this area. Therefore, in this case, the importance of effectively continuing to work on the problem of youth and using methods to achieve positive results along this path is the rooting in our country of new thoughts and ideas, as well as the moral, spiritual, social and legal views of the new generation are becoming increasingly important in terms of needs implementation of such tasks as maintaining a modern system.

As noted above, in the course of successive reforms, educating young people in the spirit of national values, loyalty to national spirituality and the desire for innovation embodied historicity and modernity.

The issue of formation and development of personal qualities is one of the priority areas of activity in this area. This, in turn, largely determines the future and development of the country and at the same time provides a solid foundation for raising young people with all-round potential, so that they become masters of a particular profession or field.

The new version of the law “On State Policy towards Youth in the Republic of Uzbekistan” adopted in our country embodies the leading content and essence of activities in this direction. This Law describes ways to systematically eliminate existing problems, and also defines the following tasks:

- phased implementation of state youth policy in accordance with the process;
- expansion and improvement of the network of state and non-state structures pursuing youth policy, strengthening their activities in the field of youth education;
- Create favorable conditions so that young people can fully demonstrate their creative potential on the path to building a great future for Uzbekistan.

This law defines the principles for implementing state youth policy in terms of fulfilling tasks in this area. It is extremely important that special attention is paid to ensuring the direct participation of young people in the development and implementation of programs related to the life of the younger generation, and further increasing their political activity.

The issue of combating information threats rises to the level of public policy in our country. In modern conditions of highly developed information technologies, the creation of a secure information environment is gaining momentum. It is worth noting that 17 regulatory documents, 9 decrees and resolutions of the President, 14 resolutions of the Cabinet of Ministers, as well as relevant norms and many interdepartmental regulatory legal documents related to the field of information security, have been adopted.

The development and implementation of the “Digital Uzbekistan-2030” program in Uzbekistan, first of all, will serve to create a “Safe Information Society” environment in the country through the formation of solid and perfect organizational and legal mechanisms.

On April 15, 2022, Article 3 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Cybersecurity”, consisting of Chapter 8, Article 40, names the basic concepts of “information space” and its connection. Some related technical and philosophical concepts are defined. Information space is

defined as a virtual environment created with the help of information technology. The concept of “Information space” (eng. Cyberspace) consists of two parts: “Cyber” and “Space”. These words are mentioned in the Oxford English Dictionary. Literally translated from Greek, *kyβernétes* means “rulers.”

The main purpose of this law is to regulate relations in the field of information security, while the following principles are observed:

Legitimacy, which means ensuring information security, the requirements of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, this Law and other legislative documents must be observed without deviations and their implementation, any deviation from the strict implementation and compliance with legal requirements, which are the reasons for this. Despite this, this is a violation of the law and it has been established that it entails the prescribed liability. In general, “legality is the unwavering compliance with laws and legal documents issued in accordance with them by all government bodies, officials and other persons. Legitimacy is one of the elements of democracy and the rule of law.”

The priority of protecting the interests of the individual, society and the state in the information space is to prevent violations of the interests of the individual, society and the state when protecting from internal and external information threats and giving them special importance. Protecting the interests of the individual, society and the state is the main task of the state and legislation. This principle is also followed by the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan and other legal documents.

At present time in the information space there are several forms of information threats to individuals, society and the state. The information space is used by various political forces as the main weapon for their terrorist and extremist campaigns and ideas, for promoting their views among the population, and for carrying out the activities of various criminal groups.

The fact that the main negative forces have created their own ideological space on the Internet, are conducting large-scale information terrorism on the Internet - “electronic jihad”, creating new threats and problems, creating problems for the countries of the world.

Conclusions and recommendations. By summarizing it can be said that it is extremely important to pay special attention to aspects related to the social characteristics of young people, their physical and spiritual changes, emotional states and behavior.

Various studies and trainings, campaigns and promotional activities, various types of promotions and advertising campaigns based on specific programs and plans are used collectively based on specific programs and plans. It is still widely used as a tool and will continue to be. be important.

REFERENCES

1. From the festive congratulations of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the youth of Uzbekistan, dated June 30, 2023 on the occasion of “June 30 – Youth Day”.
2. A project, the goal of which is ensuring the future and employment of young people. Society, June 28, 2018.
3. Speech by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the ceremony, dedicated to the 24th anniversary of the adoption of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. People's Word, December 8, 2016

4. Speech by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the ceremony, dedicated to the 24th anniversary of the adoption of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. People's Word, December 8, 2016
5. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On state policy regarding youth in the Republic of Uzbekistan.”, dated 09.14.2016.
6. Oxford English Dictionary. Oxford, 2010.
7. <https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/Legislation/>.
8. Berkinov O.T. Objective foundations and theoretical analysis of the transformation of cyberspace in the field of threats // Research summit. (2022), Pp.1042-1046.